

Quantum Wavefunction and Fluctuation of Classical Action Part II

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The classical Lagrangian L leads to Newton's second law which is equivalent to an energy-momentum conservation equation. The classical action: $A = \int dt L(t)$ for a constant velocity $v=X/T$ may be varied with respect X and T i.e. $dA/dT = -E$ and $dA/dX = p$. Thus, one may create a differential equation in $(dA/dT)(dA/dt)$ and dA/dx for the $E = p^2/m + V(x)$ equation. Alternatively, one may create other differential equations.

Quantum mechanical differential equations, however, are quite different with $\exp(i \text{Action})$ being a solution. Even this may be written as the solution of a non-Schrodinger equation i.e. $i\hbar d/dt \exp(i \text{Action}) = -1/2m (d/dx \exp(i \text{Action})) (d/dx \exp(i \text{Action}))$ for a free particle. For a constant velocity, $\exp(i \text{Action})$ is equivalent to $\exp(ipx - iEt)$. We argue that this solution is statistical because it separates x and t (as independent variables) and holds for all x and t . Thus, quantum mechanics seems to be a statistical approach using free solutions $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ to create an ensemble as in classical statistical mechanics. A difference, however, is that $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ "interferes" even if one only takes the real part $\cos(px - Et)$.

We consider the case of a particle in a box with infinite potential walls to argue that the periodicity is warranted i.e. positive and negative values (interference).

Even though the modulus is 1, $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ may be operated on by various generators e.g. d/dx the generator of translations. This is analogous to operations on vectors in linear algebra.

As noted above, quantum equations are not only energy-momentum conservation equations. They yield a wavefunction $W(x)$ which is an unusual momentum distribution $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. $\exp(-iEt)$ holds overall because average E is the same at each x . Thus, one needs a $W(x)$ which leads to a momentum-energy conservation equation, but also satisfies certain boundary conditions which become linked to spatial density $= W^*W$. This leads to discrete energy levels and also cases of humps and troughs in $W(x)$.

We attempt to investigate some of these ideas in this note.

Classical Action and Lagrangian

The Lagrangian is used in classical mechanics to obtain Newton's second law of motion which for energy conservation is equivalent to $E = KE(x) + V(x)$ for all E .

The Lagrange equations follow by varying the classical action $A = \int dt L$ where L usually equals $T - V$.

If one considers a constant velocity $v=X/T$ and varies A , the action, independently with respect to X and T (which already breaks the constraint $v=X/T$) one finds:

$$dA/dT = -E \quad \text{and} \quad dA/dX = p \quad ((1))$$

Differential Equations

Given the result ((1)), one may use an energy-momentum conservation equation such as:

$E = p^2/m + V(x)$ or $E = KE$ for a free particle ((2)) and insert ((1))

Alternatively, if a potential is present in the nonrelativistic case, one may write a differential equation using:

$W = \exp(-iEt) \exp(i \int_0^x p(x) dx)$ where $p(x)^2/2m = KE(x)$ ((2))

i.e. $i \hbar \frac{d}{dt} W = \text{Real} \left\{ -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W \right\}$ ((3))

This is not the Schrodinger equation because of the “Real” operation, but is similar. In both cases ((1)) and ((2)), one has differential equations to describe energy-momentum conservation, but neither are based on statistical considerations linked to spatial density. There are still other differential equations which may be written if one is only interested in an energy-momentum relation.

Statistical Considerations Linked to Spatial Density

It seems that quantum mechanics utilizes statistical ideas related to spatial density. For a free particle, one may argue that $P(x) = \text{constant}$, but there may be “internal motion”. Then, $W = \exp(-iEt + ipx)$ may describe the statistical situation throughout space and time with the two being independent. Time is related to energy and space to energy flow for a particle with constant v . This already breaks the constraint $v = x/t$ and may be seen as a statistical quantity. Thus, we argue that one does not necessarily need to focus on phase velocity which tries to link x and t . Neither does one need to focus on a wave packet.

One may ask why one needs an object like $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ in the first place.

The following differential equation, for example, may be formed:

$i \hbar \frac{d}{dt} \exp(-iEt - ipx) = -\frac{1}{2m} \left[\frac{d}{dx} \exp(-iEt + ipx) \right] \left[\frac{d}{dx} \exp(-iEt + ipx) \right]$ ((2b))

This is not the Schrodinger equation, but works for a free particle. An issue arises if one wishes to consider a potential and still maintain a statistical picture. It seems that if one has a potential, one wishes to create a momentum ensemble just as in classical physics. $\exp(-iEt)$ may represent the average energy at each x , but one needs a momentum distribution. If one uses $\exp(ipx)$ then a distribution is:

Sum over p $a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$

Space weight enters through $W(x)$ the normalization, but also through $\exp(ipx)$. There is no acceleration in this picture, but average kinetic energy must vary from point to point through $E = KE(x) + V(x)$. One may write this as:

$E W = V(x) W + \text{Sum over } p \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx)$ ((2c))

Given that W^*W is density one may multiply ((2b)) by W^* and obtain a term VW^*W . It is more interesting, however, to write $V(x)$ as a Fourier series (giving it statistical properties) and obtain:

$$\frac{1}{2m} \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad ((2d))$$

In this case, one cannot really distinguish between an $\exp(ipx)$ that is free or is being combined with a $V_k \exp(ikx)$ to form an $\exp(i(p+k)x)$. Thus, if one knocks out a particle from a bound state and finds it has momentum p , it may have been in a free $\exp(ipx)$ state or in a combined state with the potential. Thus, one does not really know momentum and position at the same time for a free state. A free state is a combination of $V_k \exp(ikx)$ and various $a(p_j)\exp(ip_j x)$'s.

In the probability approach, spatial density for a constant velocity particle is W^*W which is similar to the magnitude squared of a vector in linear algebra. This suggests that one may operate on the vector with various operators. In some cases an operator does not change the magnitude. One may also operate on $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ with various operators i.e. id/dt and $-id/dx$. The latter is $-i$ times the generator of a translation and yields p describing the energy flow rate in this translation direction. The id/dt and $-id/dx$ operators follow directly from the classical action. Thus, $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is statistical and leads to various eigenequations in terms of energy and energy flow which are the two key quantities in energy-momentum conservation equations.

One may wonder why $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ yields a modulus of 1 for a free v constant particle, but is very different for a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls. There is zero probability for such a particle to be outside the walls and so there would be a discontinuity in W if it were only $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ in the interior. It must become zero at the walls too. The free solution for a particle moving in one direction is $\exp(ipx-iEt)$, but there are two directions and this solution is statistical i.e. it holds for all x and t . Thus, there must be a combined $\exp(ipx-iEt)$, $\exp(-ipx-iEt)$ solution which drops to zero at the walls. This happens automatically because $\exp(ipx)$ is periodic in px , but only for certain p values (p here is actually $pave$.) Thus, $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ is a statistical solution which not only has a modulus of 1, but satisfies the scenario of a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls.

How does this differ from the classical case? There, one has a single particle which moves at a constant velocity (any velocity from 0 to c). It bounces off the wall (decelerates and then accelerates). One is not concerned with density and so there is no issue that the velocity is constant right until the wall, but 0 outside. In quantum mechanics, the effect of the wall is to create a momentum distribution which may interfere so as to create the boundary condition. There is no concept of deceleration in a momentum distribution (because time and x have been made independent) to stop the particle from going through the wall. (In non-infinite potential walls, the distribution does go through the wall, but drops rapidly.) One cannot have positive only probabilities for $P(p/x)$ i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ because one must obtain 0 from $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Here $a(p)$ is a Fourier transform of $\cos(px)$ inside the box and 0 outside. Thus, there must be interference. This suggests a $P(p/x)$ or $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ which may be positive and negative for a given p at different x values, or specific p values that have $P(p/x)$ always positive or negative for all x . The latter would be unusual because such p would only contribute

negative $p^2/2m a(p)\exp(ipx)/W$ at each x . Thus, a periodic $P(p/x)$ for a given p over x seems more reasonable.

If one ignores the boundary condition, $EW = -1/2m d/dx d/dx W$ with $W = A\cos(px)$ has every p as a solution, just as in the classical case. Quantum mechanics is different in that there is no acceleration of a particle, only a distribution of free particle $\exp(ipx)$'s which interfere. This statistical scenario which accounts for average energy i.e. $EW = -1/2m d/dx dW/dx$ must also yield a vanishing W related to physical density W^*W at the boundaries of the box. This, it seems, this requires a W which may "turn" abruptly as in a $\cos(px)$ function etc. Even for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, many $\exp(ipx)$ s may interfere to create a $\cos(\text{pave } x)$ which itself has humps and troughs (1). (This is similar to the oscillator case.) It is the potential in both cases which may stir up the momentum distribution.

Density Considerations

For a constant velocity, $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ already shows possible physical impact. $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ has been argued to be statistical and to hold for all x and t . Thus, if there is a two slit situation, one may calculate $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ for two paths, one through one slit, one through the other and arriving at the same point on a screen. There is interference in such a case. There is also interference, however, in the case of a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls. $\exp(i \text{ pave } x)$ and $\exp(-i \text{ pave } x)$ may both be applied and so one obtains $2\cos(px)$ (for example). Given that $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ "squared" is related to density, $\cos(px)$ should vanish at endpoints so that its square is also zero at these points. There is no longer equal probability to be at any x point. Thus, W (where $W^*W = \text{density}$) introduces a second constraint in quantum mechanical differential equations such as the Schrodinger equation. It is not simply energy that is conserved at each x point, but W must satisfy certain boundary conditions so that its square also satisfies physical boundary conditions.

To examine this in more detail, consider a nonrelativistic case including a potential $V(x)$. In keeping with a statistical picture, an ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$ terms is used where p may be positive or negative. in such a case, one has:

$$W(x,t) = \exp(-iEt) \text{ Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

Here again one has t and x separated. We argue that the interpretation of $\exp(-iEt)$ is that one has constant E regardless of x i.e. at each x point. Then:

$$E = -1/2m \ d/dx \ dW/dx / W + V(x) \quad ((5))$$

Here, p in $\exp(ipx)$ represents physical momentum, but $W(x)$ is also a Fourier series of function whose curvature satisfies and energy-momentum relationship, but whose values satisfy boundary conditions i.e. W must be zero at the endpoints of an infinite potential box, and must drop rapidly to zero for an oscillator. This extra constraint leads to only certain functions which can satisfy both conditions i.e. to discrete energy levels.

Humps and Troughs and Periodicity

Introducing $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ as a statistical term immediately leads to the idea of a wavelength proportional to $1/p$. Even with interference, a hump and trough pattern may be maintained as in the case of a particle in a box with an infinite potential or an oscillator potential. Changing curvature leads to a change of the number of humps (and their curvature) in the solution with a similar boundary condition holding, but with different turning points. In quantum mechanics, it may be difficult to picture the interference. For a photon, one may picture an electric field which behaves as $\cos(k(t-z))$ and so positive and negative values in a wavefunction $E+iB$ (E =electric field, B magnetic) are not so unusual, although still strange.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the classical action A for a constant velocity particle yields the relations:

$$dA/dT = -E \text{ and } dA/dX = p \text{ for } v=X/T \text{ with } X \text{ and } T \text{ being independent}$$

X and T are not independent so any differential equation which uses the above results should not be interpreted in the usual classical sense of $x(t)$, $v(t)$ etc.

Using dA/dT and dA/dX , various differential equations may be constructed by linking with energy-momentum conservation equations e.g. $E^2=p^2+m^2$ or $E=pp/2m$.

We argue that the Schrodinger quantum equation is different in that it goes beyond simply satisfying an energy-momentum equation. It introduces a statistical function based on A which is linked to spatial density. This link, it seems, forces it to be periodic in p , leads to interference and to discrete energy levels. Consider $\exp(-iET+ipx)$ which is equivalent to $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ for a constant v particle. This factor has a modulus of 1 which is statistical i.e. a free particle can be anywhere in space or time with equal probability. One may ask, however, why $P(x)=\text{constant}$ is not sufficient. A reason is that one is attempting to combine a function linked to spatial density which also yields E and p when acted on by id/dT and $-id/dX$.

One may see the idea of interference and periodicity more clearly if one considers a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls. The particle cannot be outside the walls, but $\exp(ipx-iEt)$, it was argued, describes constant p inside with p being $-p$ or p . Thus, $\exp(-ipx-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ must yield: $\exp(-iEt) \text{ function}(x)$ where $\text{function}(x)$ is zero at the endpoints. This suggests periodicity in p i.e wavelength proportional to $1/p$ with only special p values satisfying this condition i.e. discrete energy levels. (Note: spatial density is W^*W , but W e.g. $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ for a free particle already describes much of the physics.)

References

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